

BAYESIAN POISSON VECTOR AUTOREGRESSIVE MODEL TO EXPLORE THE DYNAMIC INTERRELATIONSHIP AMONG HIV/AIDS, TUBERCULOSIS, AND HEPATITIS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study employs a Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive (BAPVAR) model to investigate the dynamic interrelationships and mutual influences among HIV/AIDS, Tuberculosis (TB), and Hepatitis (HPT) diseases in Nigeria from 2004 to 2023. By capturing the temporal dependencies and forecast error variances, the analysis reveals complex interactions that underscore the significance of integrated disease control programs. The trend analysis revealed a statistically significant decrease in the prevalence of all three diseases over the study period. For each year that passed, the expected log count of HIV cases decreased by approximately 3.9%, TB cases by 8.2%, and Hepatitis cases by 2.2%. The BaP-VAR/Log-VAR models showed that all three diseases exhibit strong and statistically significant meaning the prevalence in the previous year is a powerful predictor of the current year's prevalence. A significant cross-disease dynamic was identified: a 1% increase in TB prevalence in the prior year was associated with a 0.3762% decrease in HIV prevalence in the current year. Other cross-effects between the diseases were not found to be statistically significant. The forecast error variance decomposition showed that while each disease's own shocks were the main driver of its variance, shocks to TB prevalence explained a substantial and growing portion of the variance in HIV prevalence over time.

Introduction

Infectious diseases remain a significant burden on global health, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, where HIV/AIDS,

Tuberculosis (TB), and Hepatitis continue to be major public health concerns. Nigeria ranks among the highest burden countries for these diseases, with complex interactions that

exacerbate their individual and collective impacts. Understanding the dynamic interrelationship among these diseases is crucial to formulating effective control and management strategies.

Nigeria, identified as a high burden country for HIV/AIDS, TB, and Hepatitis infections, continues to face public health challenges attributed to these diseases. The persistent co-infections and opportunistic infections in people living with HIV underscore the need to understand the interactions among these illnesses.

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) attacks the immune system, increasing vulnerability to opportunistic infections such as TB and various forms of hepatitis. Co-infections significantly alter disease progression, transmission dynamics, and treatment outcomes. For instance, about one-third of TB patients in Nigeria are estimated to also be infected with HIV, indicating strong epidemiological links (Bevilacqua et al., 2002). The interaction between these diseases influences their natural history and pathogenesis, thereby amplifying the overall disease burden (Jacob et al., 2013). Unlike other HIV co-infections, TB is readily transmissible and its incidence rises rapidly following HIV seroconversion (Sonnenberg et al., 2005).

Traditional univariate analyses often fail to capture the bidirectional and lagged effects between these diseases. The Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive (BAPVAR) model offers an advanced statistical approach to jointly model multiple time series count data, accounting for

simultaneous interactions, dependencies, and feedback loops while accommodating the inherent uncertainty in disease incidence data. This approach facilitates a better understanding of disease dynamics over time and the potential influences diseases exert on each other.

Nigeria's high burden of HIV/AIDS, TB, and Hepatitis—coupled with emerging infections and limited healthcare resources—emphasizes the need for sophisticated modeling to inform public health policy and intervention programs. By applying the BAPVAR model to data collected from the Federal Medical Center, Jabi, Abuja, between 2004 and 2023, this study aims to elucidate the complex temporal interdependencies among these three diseases and provide insights into their co-dynamics.

Statement of the Problem

Therefore, the central problem this study addresses is the need for a comprehensive and integrated modeling framework, specifically employing the Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, to unravel the dynamics and prevalence of infectious diseases in Nigeria. This approach seeks to bridge the gap between traditional disease modeling methods and the complex reality of disease interactions, external influences, and population-specific factors, with the ultimate goal of informing evidence-based policies that can enhance disease management, healthcare planning, and overall public health outcomes in the country. Although previous studies have modeled scenarios using the Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive Model, such as the work by Fagbemi, Esther Temidayo under the supervision of Dr.

Adenomon, who applied this model to analyze the dynamics of AIDS-related diseases at Plateau State Special Hospital (PSSH) in Jos, Nigeria, from 2003 to 2018, the current study applies a similar model but differs in its case study and time frame. Specifically, this research focuses on the Federal Medical Center (FMC) Jabi in Abuja, Nigeria, covering the period from 2004 to 2023. The motivation for selecting FMC Abuja as the case study is the researcher's interest in understanding how the selected diseases interact in a different environment, particularly in the capital city of Nigeria. Additionally, Patrick (2011) developed a Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive model to investigate endogenous dynamic relationships among event count time series, focusing on terrorism in developed economies. Similarly, this study employs the Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive Model to model the dynamics of the prevalence of infectious diseases at the Federal Medical Center.

Aim

The aim of the study is to utilize the Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model to analyze and unravel the complex interrelationships between HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis (TB), and hepatitis infections in Nigeria. This advanced modeling approach seeks to capture the simultaneous interactions, lags, and feedback loops among these infectious diseases over time, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of their transmission dynamics and co-infection patterns.

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To employ the Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model to analyze the interdependencies between HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis (TB), and hepatitis infections in Nigeria.
2. To capture the simultaneous interactions, lags, and feedback loops among these infectious diseases over time, providing a holistic understanding of their dynamics.

Research Methodology

Log-VAR (1) Model

	Log (HIV)	Log (Hpt)	Log (TB)
Log (HIV)_{t-1}	0.538730 (0.20806) [2.58927]	-0.090216 (0.18702) [-0.48240]	-0.442337 (0.43155) [-1.02501]
Log (Hpt)_{t-1}	0.438091 (0.30822) [1.42136]	0.816121 (0.27704) [2.94583]	-0.109971 (0.63928) [-0.17202]
Log (TB)_{t-1}	-0.376208 (0.16203) [-2.32186]	-0.210390 (0.14564) [-1.44460]	0.607877 (0.33607) [1.80880]
Intercept	3.844408 (0.98571) [3.90016]	2.436650 (0.88600) [2.75018]	3.395903 (2.04446) [1.66102]

Source: Author’s Computation 2024.

Table 4.6 displayed that Log(HIV)_{t-1} has a Coefficient of 0.538730, Standard Error of 0.20806 and t-Statistic of 2.58927. The coefficient for Log(HIV)_{t-1} is 0.5387, which is positive and statistically significant (t-statistic > 2). This suggests that a 1% increase in HIV prevalence in the previous period is associated with a 0.5387% increase in HIV prevalence in the current period, indicating persistence in HIV prevalence over time.

The Log(Hpt)_{t-1} has a Coefficient of 0.438091, Standard Error of 0.30822 and t-Statistic of 1.42136. The coefficient for Log(Hpt)_{t-1} is 0.4381, which is positive but not statistically significant (t-statistic < 2). This indicates a potential but not significant positive association

between past hepatitis prevalence and current HIV prevalence.

The Log(TB)_{t-1} has a Coefficient of -0.376208, Standard Error of 0.16203 and t-Statistic of -2.32186. The coefficient for Log(TB)_{t-1} is -0.3762, which is negative and statistically significant (t-statistic < -2). This suggests that a 1% increase in TB prevalence in the previous period is associated with a 0.3762% decrease in HIV prevalence in the current period.

The intercept of has a Coefficient of 3.844408, Standard Error of 0.98571 and t-Statistic of 3.90016. The intercept is 3.8444, which is positive and statistically significant (t-statistic > 2). This represents the baseline log(HIV) value when all lagged variables are zero.

Again, the Log(HIV)_{t-1} has the Coefficient of -0.090216, Standard Error of 0.18702 and t-Statistic of -0.48240. The coefficient for Log(HIV)_{t-1} is -0.0902, which is negative but not statistically significant (t-statistic > -2). This indicates no significant effect of past HIV prevalence on current hepatitis prevalence.

Log(Hpt)_{t-1} has the Coefficient of 0.816121, Standard Error of 0.27704 and t-Statistic 2.94583. The coefficient for Log(Hpt)_{t-1} is 0.8161, which is positive and statistically significant (t-statistic > 2). This suggests that a 1% increase in hepatitis prevalence in the previous period is associated with a 0.8161% increase in hepatitis prevalence in the current period, indicating persistence in hepatitis prevalence over time.

Log(TB)_{t-1} has Coefficient of -0.210390, Standard Error: 0.14564 and t-Statistic: -1.44460. The coefficient for Log(TB)_{t-1} is -0.2104, which is negative but not statistically significant (t-statistic > -2). This indicates no significant effect of past TB prevalence on current hepatitis prevalence.

The intercept has Coefficient of 2.436650, Standard Error of 0.88600 and t-Statistic of 2.75018. The intercept is 2.4367, which is positive and statistically significant (t-statistic > 2). This represents the baseline log(HPT) value when all lagged variables are zero

Log(HIV)_{t-1} Coefficient: -0.442337 Standard Error: 0.43155 and t-Statistic: -1.02501. The coefficient for Log(HIV)_{t-1} is -0.4423, which is negative but not statistically significant (t-statistic > -2). This indicates no significant effect

of past HIV prevalence on current TB prevalence.

Log(Hpt)_{t-1} with the Coefficient of -0.109971, Standard Error: 0.63928 and t-Statistic: -0.17202. The coefficient for Log(Hpt)_{t-1} is -0.1100, which is negative but not statistically significant (t-statistic > -2). This indicates no significant effect of past hepatitis prevalence on current TB prevalence.

Log(TB)_{t-1} has the Coefficient: 0.607877, Standard Error: 0.33607 and t-Statistic: 1.80880. The coefficient for Log(TB)_{t-1} is 0.6079, which is positive but not statistically significant (t-statistic < 2). This suggests a potential positive association between past and current TB prevalence, but it is not statistically significant.

The intercept has the Coefficient of 3.395903, Standard Error: 2.04446 and t-Statistic: 1.66102. The intercept is 3.3959, which is positive but not statistically significant (t-statistic < 2). This represents the baseline log(TB) value when all lagged variables are zero. In conclusion the variables Log(HIV) and Log(HPT) show significant persistence over time (their lagged values have positive and statistically significant coefficients). There is a significant negative relationship between past TB prevalence and current HIV prevalence. Other cross-effects between HIV, HPT, and TB are not statistically significant, suggesting no strong evidence of influence from one disease's prevalence on the other's in this model. All intercepts are positive, with the intercept for Log(HIV) and Log(HPT) being statistically significant. Overall, the results suggest that past

values of the same disease are significant predictors of current prevalence for HIV and HPT, highlighting the persistence in their prevalence over time.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The study reveals a coefficient -0.0390903 , Standard error of 0.0017984 , z-value of -21.74 and $P > |z|: 0.000$, indicating that the coefficient is highly statistically significant. Meaning that for every one-unit increase in Time, the expected log count of HIV decreases by approximately 0.039 . This suggests that as time progresses, the HIV counts are expected to decrease. The study also shows that for every one-unit increase in Time, the expected log count of TB decreases by approximately 0.082 . This suggests that as time progresses, the TB counts are expected to decrease significantly. Again, based on the report from the output it was discovered that for every one-unit increase in Time, the expected log count of HPT decreases by approximately 0.0225 . This suggests that as time progresses, the HPT counts are expected to decrease. On the disease relationship, it was noted that the coefficient for lagged HIV as 0.9201 , indicating that the HIV prevalence in the current period is strongly influenced by its prevalence in the previous period. Although both TB and hepatitis show positive relationships with HIV prevalence, but these relationships are not statistically significant due to high uncertainty and wide credible intervals. Similarly, the Mean of past TB value (0.9192) which indicated that the Past TB prevalence strongly predicts current TB prevalence, indicating high persistence over

time. Finally, the Coeff. of (0.9224) value of Past HPT prevalence strongly predicts current HPT prevalence, indicating high persistence over time. The high persistence of HPT prevalence over time is statistically significant, suggesting past HPT prevalence is a strong predictor of current prevalence. The slightly negative trend in HPT prevalence over time is not statistically significant. The results emphasize the significant persistence of HPT prevalence over time while showing that other variables like HIV and TB do not have a statistically significant impact on HPT prevalence.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from this study, the researcher concludes that significant relationship exist between HIV/AIDS, TB and HPT as increase in one brings about increase or decrease in another, also a significant decrease of 3.9% and 8.2% respectively were realized. Furthermore, the results showed a significant decrease of 2.2% in Hepatitis. Lastly, the results emphasize the significant persistence of HPT prevalence over time while showing that other variables like HIV and TB do not have a statistically significant impact on HPT prevalence.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following are recommended that;

- i. Policymakers should adopt data-driven approaches in public health decision-making. The Bayesian Poisson Vector Autoregressive Model provides valuable insights that can guide the development of targeted interventions and resource distribution.

ii. Since Hepatitis rate isn't declining as reflected in the data set, the government and stakeholders in the health sector should create

iii. Government should increase investment in healthcare infrastructure, particularly in biostatistics and epidemiological research capabilities. This will enhance the ability of health facilities like FMC Jabi to collect and analyze data, leading to more effective disease control measures.

enlightenment campaigns on vaccination and possible preventive measures.

Limitations of the Study

The researcher encountered several limitations during the study. Firstly, data sets prior to 2004 were unavailable. Additionally, the research model, which has not yet been extensively utilized by scholars, made finding relevant material on the statistical model challenging. Lastly, the data was sourced from only one secondary health care facility.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: PREVALENCE OF HIV/AIDS, TB AND HEPATITIS BY YEAR

Time	HIV	TB	HPT
2004	83	19	137
2005	247	65	325
2006	1050	214	485
2007	1431	221	521
2008	167	149	380
2009	132	266	464
2010	270	255	557
2011	1103	137	214
2012	544	56	156
2013	705	101	323
2014	796	71	509
2015	568	52	251
2016	348	10	221
2017	506	16	311
2018	559	28	645
2019	205	2	290
2020	365	18	423
2021	243	75	231
2022	123	43	79
2023	141	89	132

Source: Federal Medical Center, Jabi, Abuja. Nigeria (2024).

Appendix B

Table 4.1: Trend analysis of HIV/AIDs

. poisson HIV Time

Iteration 0: log likelihood = -2399.472

Iteration 1: log likelihood = -2399.472

Poisson regression

Number of obs = 20

LR chi2(1) = 479.70

Prob > chi2 = 0.0000

Pseudo R2 = 0.0909

Log likelihood = -2399.472

HIV	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
Time	-.0390903	.0017984	-21.74	0.000	-.042615	-.0355655
_cons	84.85531	3.618722	23.45	0.000	77.76274	91.94787

Source: STAT 17 output 2024

Table 4.2: Trend analysis of Tuberculosis (TB)

. poisson TB Time

Iteration 0: log likelihood = -565.10206

Iteration 1: log likelihood = -565.10203

Poisson regression

Number of obs = 20

LR chi2(1) = 397.13

Prob > chi2 = 0.0000

Pseudo R2 = 0.2600

Log likelihood = -565.10203

TB	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
Time	-.0821983	.0042611	-19.29	0.000	-.0905499	-.0738467
_cons	169.9434	8.568595	19.83	0.000	153.1493	186.7376

Source: STAT 17 output 2024

Table 4.3: Trend analysis of Hepatitis (HPT)

```
. poisson HPT Time
```

Iteration 0: log likelihood = -779.48314 |
 Iteration 1: log likelihood = -779.48314

Poisson regression

Log likelihood = -779.48314

Number of obs = 20
 LR chi2(1) = 111.79
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
 Pseudo R2 = 0.0669

HPT	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
Time	-.0225353	.0021368	-10.55	0.000	-.0267234	-.0183472
_cons	51.1737	4.300902	11.90	0.000	42.74409	59.60332

Source: STAT 17 output 2024

Table 4.4: Effect of Tuberculosis and Hepatitis on HIV

Bayesian vector autoregression
 Gibbs sampling

Sample: 2005 thru 2023

Log marginal-likelihood = -150.80636

MCMC iterations = 12,500
 Burn-in = 2,500
 MCMC sample size = 10,000
 Number of obs = 19
 Acceptance rate = 1
 Efficiency: min = .6598
 avg = .8916
 max = 1

	Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE	Median	Equal-tailed [95% cred. interval]	
HIV						
HIV L1.	.9200953	.0977228	.001112	.9193739	.7308227	1.113982
Time	-.1045077	.1380749	.001419	-.1020004	-.3900959	.1648181
TB	1.02732	1.502053	.015021	1.020279	-1.958717	4.017989
HPT	.4426538	.8293795	.008419	.4478381	-1.240465	2.096315
_cons	-.1168571	10.09532	.100953	-.2181093	-19.74749	19.91887
Sigma_1_1	244650.3	107399.1	1322.17	221885	110019	523396.5

Source: STAT 17 output 2024

Table 4.5: Effect of HIV and Hepatitis on TB

```

Bayesian vector autoregression      MCMC iterations =    12,500
Gibbs sampling                       Burn-in           =     2,500
                                     MCMC sample size =   10,000
Sample: 2005 thru 2023               Number of obs     =     19
                                     Acceptance rate   =     1
                                     Efficiency: min   =    .6146
                                     avg               =    .9084
                                     max               =     1
Log marginal-likelihood = -120.52323
  
```

		Mean	Std. dev.	MCSE	Median	Equal-tailed [95% cred. interval]	
TB							
	TB						
	L1.	.9191954	.0903599	.000989	.9181516	.7395084	1.100633
	Time	-.0159192	.0204966	.000205	-.0160119	-.0564706	.0246104
	HIV	-.0247059	.0457678	.000458	-.024452	-.1172381	.0660983
	HPT	.1628821	.1077113	.001077	.1642991	-.0552395	.3715623
	_cons	-.0416731	10.07068	.100707	.0093108	-19.86831	19.48471
	Sigma_1_1	4659.899	2029.87	25.8929	4213.952	2137.98	9670.302

Source: STAT 17 output 2024

Table 4.6: Effect of HIV and TB on Hepatitis

Bayesian vector autoregression	MCMC iterations =	12,500
Gibbs sampling	Burn-in =	2,500
	MCMC sample size =	10,000
Sample: 2005 thru 2023	Number of obs =	19
	Acceptance rate =	1
	Efficiency: min =	.5732
	avg =	.8913
	max =	1
Log marginal-likelihood = -138.29968		

		Coeff.	Std. dev.	MCSE	Median	Equal-tailed [95% cred. interval]
HPT	HPT					
	L1.	.922371	.0996436	.001102	.9218365	.7299147 1.11861
	Time	-.0109294	.0490586	.000502	-.0099455	-.1122717 .0847662
	HIV	.0357064	.1435292	.001408	.0358918	-.2461707 .3223531
	TB	.3259077	.6358788	.006359	.3364524	-.9401342 1.585159
	_cons	-.0887655	10.09843	.100984	-.0767879	-19.72568 19.66644
	Sigma_1_1	47344.79	20915.12	276.262	42800.55	21508.58 101181

Figure 1: Orthogonalized IRF graph.